

Maximising the Number of Secured Users in an Integrated Quantum Passive Optical Network

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Abstract—We analysed the maximum number of secured users via upstream and downstream continuous-variable and upstream discrete-variable quantum key distribution (QKD) systems coexisting with classical channels in passive optical networks. We demonstrated that downstream continuous-variable QKD outperforms upstream discrete-variable QKD only for small number of users.

Keywords—Quantum Key Distribution, Passive Optical Network, Spontaneous Raman Scattering

I. INTRODUCTION

Quantum key distribution (QKD) allows the secure exchange of cryptographic keys between distant users. Depending on the properties of the quantum information carriers, QKD protocols can be defined as discrete variable (DV) or continuous variable (CV). Furthermore, the concept of quantum access network (QAN) has been proposed to scale up the number of users in quantum secured networks [1]. QAN replicates the idea of optical access network by establishing point-to-multipoint connections between a common node and multiple end-users. In classical fibre networks, the access segment is mainly provided by cost-effective passive optical networks (PONs), which use passive splitters and fibre links reaching more than 256 users. In recent years, different studies have analysed different approaches for the quantum passive optical network (QPON). With DV QKD systems, the secret key is deterministically distributed only in upstream (US) direction, i.e. one shared quantum receiver (Bob) and multiple transmitters (Alices) that are managed by time-division multiple access (TDMA) [1]; the same time-sharing approach can be applied also to US CV-based QPONs [2]. The properties of CV QKD protocols enable, however, the independent and simultaneous key generation between one single Alice and multiple Bobs, thus realising a downstream (DS) QPON [2]. With this approach, the secret key rate (SKR) for each user is no longer limited by the TDMA time slot allocation.

The coexistence of QKD systems with classical channels in the legacy optical infrastructure is required for reducing costs and complexity of quantum networks. However, the presence of high-power signals generates in-band spontaneous Raman scattering (SpRS) noise affecting the quantum performance. Previous work in point-to-point scenarios showed that CV QKD is more resilient to excess noise, whereas DV QKD supports higher losses [3]. The deployment of QANs in already existing

PONs is therefore very challenging due to the broad SpRS crosstalk generated by standard-compliant classical channels and to the high losses introduced by the splitters. An increasing number of works have investigated these issues [4-7]. However, a comprehensive analysis of different QPON protocols in practical scenarios is still missing. In this paper, we compare SKR and supported number of users for US DV QKD, US CV QKD and DS CV QKD systems coexisting with GPON, XG-PON, NG-PON2 or HS-PON classical channels in single-fibre PONs.

II. METHODS

The considered PON architecture includes a feeder fibre connecting the central office (CO) to one optical splitter, followed by drop fibres that reach the end-users located at the optical network units (ONUs). The split ratio of the optical splitter is the inverse of the number of ONUs in the PON. Alice and Bob are placed either at the CO or at the ONU side accordingly to the chosen QPON protocols. In US, the security analyses defined for point-to-point connections are implemented: gaussian modulated coherent state CV QKD under collective attack in trusted heterodyne receiver scenario [8] and decoy-state BB84 protocol for DV QKD [9]. Considering the impact of the TDMA and assuming that the QKD service is required by all the end-users connected to the network, the calculated SKRs are therefore divided by the total number of ONUs. For the DS CV QPON, the untrusted broadcast protocol presented in [2] is implemented, considering the same receiver techniques of the US CV system. The performance of the QPON protocols is strongly affected by the transmittance of the quantum channel and by the in-band SpRS noise generated by the coexistence with DS and US classical channels. In a PON infrastructure, the transmittance is obtained by multiplying the propagation losses by the split ratio; the SpRS spectral density is estimated through the model proposed in [5] using only one splitting level. Finally, from the SpRS spectral density the excess noise [10] and the background count rate [11] are derived for CV and DV QKD, respectively.

TABLE I. CLASSICAL AND QUANTUM CHANNEL SPECIFICATIONS: CLASSICAL DS (US) $\lambda_c^{DS(US)}$ AND QUANTUM λ_Q WAVELENGTH IN [NM], CLASSICAL DS (US) LAUNCH POWER $P_c^{DS(US)}$ IN [DBM]

	λ_c^{DS}	P_c^{DS}	λ_c^{US}	P_c^{US}	λ_Q
GPON	1480	5.5	1290	5.2	1280
XG-PON	1575	4.5	1280	5.2	1420
NG-PON2	1596	5.5	1524	7.2	1310
HS-PON	1344	9	1310	7.2	1675

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Fig. 1. Secret key rate per user as a function of the number of users in a 10-km long QPON for US DV QKD (dotted line), US CV QKD (dashed line) and DS CV QKD (solid line) in coexistence with PON-compliant classical channels. DV QKD parameters: signal average intensity $\mu = 0.6$, misalignment error probability $e_{mis} = 3.2e-3$, error correction efficiency $f_e = 1.15$, single-photon detector dark count rate $p_d = 1e-6$, Bob bandpass filter $\Delta\nu = 12.5$ GHz, Bob gate interval $\Delta t = 1$ ns, Bob transmittance $\eta_{DV} = 0.16$. CV QKD parameters: modulation variance $V_A = 8$ SNU, trusted electronic noise $V_{el} = 63$ mSNU, reconciliation efficiency $\beta = 0.95$, background excess noise $\xi_{bg} = 0.2$ mSNU, Bob transmittance $\eta_{CV} = 0.44$.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We developed a simulation tool that evaluates the QPON performance in a network infrastructure with variable feeder fiber length and here provide results obtained with 9-km long feeder fibre and 1-km long drop fibre. The coexisting classical channel specifications are compliant with the corresponding PON standards and reported in Tab. 1. The spectral allocations of the QKD channel (Tab. 1) belong to the quantum-available bandwidth obtained in [5]. The QKD system parameters are specified in the caption of Fig. 1. The number of ONUs has a triple role in an integrated QPON: decreasing the channel transmittance, modifying the generation of SpRS and reducing the time-slot duration for each end-user in US protocols. Fig. 1 shows the SKRs per user as a function of the number of end-users (up to 64) in coexistence with GPON, XG-PON, NG-PON2 or HS-PON classical channels. The SKRs are expressed in terms of bit/channel use, and thus the final SKR will be proportional to the repetition rate of the network. Generally, CV PON protocols result in higher SKRs in a network with limited number of users; in particular, the advantage of simultaneous key generation with DS CV QKD over the time-sharing CV approach is clearly visible in Fig. 1 for all the considered scenarios. The scale factor between DS and US CV QPON, however, is not only due to the TDMA ratio, but also caused by the opposite respective directions of QKD and classical channels in the two approaches. In coexistence with GPON or XG-PON, the US CV QKD supports, in fact, an higher number of users (18 and 12, respectively) with respect to the DS CV protocol because the former experiences lower excess noise. On the contrary, when the quantum and classical spectral allocation generate similar noise levels (i.e., coexistence with NG-PON2), the ratio between the CV SKRs is almost the split ratio. For all the considered scenarios, the maximum number (up to 64) of supported users is achieved using DV QKD systems, whereas both the CV QPON protocols reach a maximum of around 20 users. This advantage increases in PON with longer fibres, typical of rural networks. Finally, due to the high SpRS noise level over the entire spectrum, the integration with XG-PON is

the most challenging scenario, where CV QKD demonstrates better robustness to crosstalk than DV QKD.

IV. CONCLUSION

The integration of QPON in the already deployed fibre networks is the most cost-efficient solution for QANs. This paper investigates the performance of several QPON protocols coexisting with standard-compliant classical channels in 10-km single-fibre PON. The maximum number of supported users is reached with US DV QKD systems, which provide for small user numbers lower SKRs than CV QKD, especially in DS CV QPON. Moreover, the coherent transceivers used in CV QKD systems better conform with the QAN demands as for costs and footprint.

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